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Sustainable Management of Tanguar Haor Resources: Community-based Tourism as an Alternative

June, 2015

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Dhaka
July, 2015

Syed Rashidul Hasan
and Md Saiful Islam

Acronyms

AIGAs	Alternative Income Generating Activities
BDT	Bangladeshi Taka (the currency of Bangladesh)
BPC	Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation
BSCIC	Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation
BTB	Bangladesh Tourism Board
BUET	Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology
CBSMTH	Community Based Sustainable Management of Tanguar Haor
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CBT	Community-Based Tourism
CITES	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
DU	Dhaka University
ECA	Ecologically Critical Area
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
GoB	Government of Bangladesh
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LIP	Livelihood Improvement Plan
MoCAT	Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism
MoEF	Ministry of Environment and Forests
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NHTTI	National Hotel and Tourism Training Institute
SCM	Social Capital Management
SDC	Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
TCC	Tourism Carrying Capacity
THMA	Tanguar Haor Management Authority
THMC	Tanguar Haor Management Committee
TOAB	Tour Operators Association of Bangladesh
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
USD	United States Dollar
USTO	Unique Selling Tourism Offers
WCED	World Commission on Environment and Development

Executive Summary

Wetlands are important not only for their role in maintaining ecological balance and biodiversity conservation but also for their contribution in providing livelihood to a large number of people around the world. Without proper management of the wetland resources, the wetland itself can be degraded and even be ruined permanently. Tanguar Haor is one of the largest wetland ecosystems of Bangladesh that has been recognised as one of the most important wetlands not only of Bangladesh but also of South Asia. Considering its critical condition as a result of overexploitation of its natural resources, it was declared Ecologically Critical Area (ECA) in 1999. Sustainable management of wetland resources can be achieved in different ways. Community-based tourism development can be one of the smartest and most effective alternatives.

Community-based tourism can certainly involve a good number of local people in tourism who would, otherwise, get involved in extracting natural resources of Tanguar Haor for their livelihood. Community-based tourism, in this way, can play a vital role in conserving nature without depriving the local community of their livelihood. In this study, potential ways for community-based tourism in Tanguar Haor has been identified and proposed for future implementation.

Tourism in Tanguar Haor is seasonal in pattern, and can be divided into winter and monsoon season. The ratio of tourists as per winter and monsoon seasons is almost 7:3. Around 8 to 10 thousand tourists visit this wetland every year and most of them are researchers and bird watchers. Leisure and recreation segment of tourists will never be attracted to this destination as there has been no infrastructure developed to accommodate the tourists for their overnight stay. As a result, Tanguar Haor has a destination only for the adventurers and researchers. At the same, it indicates a huge potential for tourism development as it is yet to develop Tanguar Haor as an ecotourism destination far different from any other destinations in Bangladesh.

Community-based tourism in Tanguar Haor must take place in particular zones, so that the ecosystems need not to suffer from tourism activities. In this study, some tourist zones have been identified and also the scopes for community involvement. But, CBT is not possible without direct and indirect assistance of a number of government and NGOs for policy, fund and training. This assistance and support should be an ongoing process. Otherwise, it has its every possibility to be an unsuccessful CBT. In this report, all the possible assistance and supports that CBT must be provided with by different actors including government, NGOs, and international development organizations have been identified.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Bangladesh is bestowed with innumerable tourism assets. Apart from the popular tourist destinations like Cox's Bazar, St. Martin island, Bandarban, Rangamati, Sundarban, Kuakata, Paharpu, Moinamoti, Sreemongal, Bagerhat etc, a huge tourism treasure is lying almost uncovered in the north-eastern part of Bangladesh. This area is upper Sylhet region mainly comprising with big waterbodies and wetlands. Locally they are known as Haors, Baors, Beels, jheels etc. Tanguar Haor is one of the beautiful waterbodies which has earned name internationally for its location, greatness, biodiversity, flora and fauna, hub of migratory birds, and its economic importance.

Tanguar Haor is one of the largest wetland ecosystems in northeast region of Bangladesh comprising of 10,000 ha of land area. It is located in the district of Sunamgonj (25°06'-25°11' N and 91°01'-91°06' E) at the foothill of the Khasi Hills. Tanguar haor is part of a complex wetland system of the Meghna and Surma river basin.

As per BirdLife International, Tanguar haor has been recognised as one of the most important wetlands not only of Bangladesh but also of South Asia (Alam, IUCN, 2012).

It is a unique ecosystem which supports nearly 200 species of wetland flora, 141 species of fish (half of the total freshwater fish species found in Bangladesh), 11 amphibians, 34 reptiles and 208 species of birds of which 98 are migratory (Mukul, 2007 quoted by IUCN, 2012). The ecological system surrounding Tanguar Haor provides livelihood to some 77,000 people spread over 88 villages (IUCN, 2011).

The Government of Bangladesh declared Tanguar haor as an Ecologically Critical Area (ECA) in 1999 considering its critical condition as a result of overexploitation of its natural resources. Later, this wetland was declared as a wetland of international importance under the Ramsar Convention in 2000 (GoB, 2004). With these declarations, the Government has reinforced its commitment to preserve the natural resources of this wetland and has taken several steps for the protection of this ecosystem.

Apart from the economic aspects of Tanguar haor and its tremendous impact on the life of surrounding people, this wetland is gradually drawing the attention of a particular segment of tourist market. The bird-watchers, freelance photographers, adventure seeking tourists are the main components of the segment. It has been reported that each year roughly 8000 to 10.000 tourists visit this wetland.

Figure 1: Map of Tanguar Haor. (Source: IUCNB, 2012. *Biodeversity of Tanguar Haor: A Ramsar Site of Bangladesh Vol II: Flora*)

Tanguar haor noticeably has three distinct seasons : Full Flood (monsoon), Post monsoon, and winter (IUCNB, 2012).

During Monsoon, huge water engulfs the whole of Tanguar haor excepting the small island-like settlements. Grass, reeds, and plants all go under the water. They remain submerged for nearly 5 months.

During Post-monsoon when the water starts receding, the and visibility of submerged lands and plants can be noticed gradually. Because of mudflats, the life of the local people is hard-hit.

During winter, the migratory birds start coming and the Tanguar haor becomes birds' paradise.

Importance of Wetland Tourism:

In recognition of the interdependence between sustainable tourism and the conservation and sustainable management of wetlands, in February 2010, United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) signed a Memorandum of Cooperation with the Secretariat of the Convention on Wetlands (www.ramsar.org). The enhanced cooperation between both organizations has been expected to facilitate the development of project proposals and joint initiatives aimed at reinforcing the role of wetlands and their biodiversity ecosystems for sustainable tourism development (UNWTO, 2010)

The Convention uses a broad definition of the types of wetlands covered in its mission, including swamps and marshes, lakes and rivers, wet grasslands and peatlands, oases, estuaries, deltas and tidal flats, near-shore marine areas, mangroves and coral reefs, and human-made sites such as fish ponds, rice paddies, reservoirs, and salt pans (Ramsar Convention Secretariat, undated). As per the Convention, mudflats, sandy beaches, salt pans are also included in the list.

Along with man-made and other different types of tourist attractions, people are attracted to water: to coastal wetlands such as coral reefs and beaches, and to inland wetlands such as lakes and rivers, and other water bodies. Wetlands and other water bodies along with their wildlife are important form of globally recognized tourism. It provides an amazing experience, from mass tourism to specialist tourism in small groups.

International tourism expenditure reached 1 trillion USD in 2011 (UNWTO press release, 7 May 2012). With half of all international tourists travelling to wetlands, especially to coastal areas, and the additional value of domestic tourism and recreational day trips, the economic value of wetland tourism is truly enormous (Ramsar and UNWTO, 2012).

On the other hand, according to the Destination Wetlands Report prepared by the World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO) and the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands it is estimated that **half of all international tourists travel to wetlands**, especially to the coast.

According to traveldailynews.com, International tourist arrivals reached 982 million in 2011 and are expected to top one billion in 2012, generating over US\$ 1 trillion in international tourism receipts. It is estimated that half of all tourists travel to wetlands, particularly coastal areas (traveldailynews.com, retrieved April, 2015).

Based on this estimate, visiting tourists to wetlands spend around US\$ 925 billion each year on wetland-related tourism. Wetlands offer a range of recreational activities include sunbathing, swimming, boating, diving, snorkeling, sport fishing, duck hunting, photography, birdwatching, and simply enjoying the landscape. Many wetlands are not just holiday destinations but are also tourist attractions themselves. For example, The Great Barrier Reef Marine Park records on average 1.8 million visitor-days per year. Wetlands are sometimes key to the economy of a region with few other opportunities for revenue generation and employment. For example, in the Everglades, in the United States, this amounts to around US\$ 450 million in direct and indirect expenditures by tourists and from employment in the tourism sector. Thus tourism is an important and visible value provided by wetlands (Anand Chandrasekhar, 2013).

Tourism businesses can help protecting wetland biodiversity:

UNWTO (2010) in one of their reports suggested that if planned and managed in proper ways, tourism rather can promote and support the wetland biodiversity in the following ways:

- reducing pollution from tourism activities, particularly by ensuring that all liquid and solid wastes are properly treated and disposed of in ways that do not result in damage to biodiversity, and by minimizing use of pesticides, fertilizers and toxic chemicals;
- obtaining all food stuffs, and other biological resources used in tourism activities, from sustainably managed sources;
- supporting biodiversity conservation by government agencies and NGOs through practical actions, including financial contributions, for example, through sponsorships and voluntary donations;
- ensuring that no invasive alien species are introduced through tourism activities;
- ensuring that no threatened or endangered species are put at risk from tourism activities or enter the tourism supply chain (especially as foods or souvenirs); and
- using the communications and marketing strengths of the tourism sector to raise awareness of tourists and destination authorities of the value of biodiversity and the steps they can take to protect it.

Apprehended negative Impacts of Wetland Tourism:

The impacts of tourism on the ecological values of wetlands may derive from tourism-related transport and infrastructure; the construction, maintenance and use of tourist accommodation and facilities; and the presence and activities of tourists in wetland areas. These impacts may be both direct and indirect; may vary from global warming and climate change to local effects such as trampling or pollution of ground water; and may be short-term or long lasting.

According to Lorton Consultancy, Some of the major environmental risks related to tourism are:

1. The construction of tourism facilities, such as hotels, lodges, restaurants, visitor centres or campsites and related infrastructure, as well as the associated problems of water and soil pollution, can seriously impact biodiversity in wetland areas.
2. Concentrated use of areas around facilities may have a negative effect on both vegetation and fauna.
3. Tourism facilities and their use require resources for tourists, such as food and water, and raw materials for building tourism infrastructure, which may be extracted from wetlands.

4. Transportation may have direct negative effects on the environment (e.g. removal of vegetation, disturbance to animals, release of oil and fuel from boats and other craft). Marine mammals may be injured or killed by impacts with boats.
5. Transportation may cause pollutions from carbon emissions and noise.
6. Visitors may disturb wildlife, including species that are not attractive to visitors, by making noise or harassing animals.
7. The sale of souvenirs made from endangered species is also destroying the beautiful natural environment that the tourists come to enjoy.

However, Wetland.Org observed that “The relationship between tourism and wetlands is however complex and sometimes adversarial. Tourism can impact wetlands in a number of ways such as by causing habitat loss, pollution, noise or over-consumption of water. But with proper planning tourism can also be an innovative mechanism for funding nature conservation and development of local livelihoods.”

In literature review we have consulted many scholarly articles, news reports, proceedings of the meetings, news clipping etc. and mostly it has been mentioned about the positive impacts of tourism in and around wetlands and similar water bodies. There are some studies which justified wetland tourism by citing data and statistics on how tourism helped alleviating lives of the people of wetlands. Nevertheless, there are also many writings where much has been said about the adversarial effects of wetland tourism. So, the question remains if we should go forward with the development of wetland tourism or not?

Wetland.Org reported that the relationship between tourism and wetlands is however complex and sometimes adversarial. Tourism can impact wetlands in a number of ways such as by causing habitat loss, pollution, noise or over-consumption of water. But with proper planning tourism can also be an innovative mechanism for funding nature conservation and development of local livelihoods.

In our opinion, tourism development is expected in Tanguar haor for the greater benefit of the local people and conservation of biodiversity. But a specific policy and clearly defined rules and regulations should be formed highlighting ‘dos and don’ts’ so that in a sustainable way and without hampering the ecology and biodiversity of this sensitive area we can satiate the lust of the nature loving tourists and at the same time ensure long-term economic benefit of the local people.

Mr. Taleb Rifai, the UNWTO Secretary-General told “Wetlands are one of tourism’s greatest assets, attracting millions of tourists each year. Working in close partnership with the Ramsar Secretariat, UNWTO is determined to sustainably manage wetland tourism through sound polices and planning, thereby conserving them for the enjoyment of generations to come.”(Traveldailynews.com)

Just simply on the apprehension of the negative impacts of tourism in one destination, we should not keep some mind-refreshing treasures undiscovered. In the same context once the tribal king of Bandarban - a beautiful tribal hilly tourism-hub of the country, Raja AungShuePrueChowdhury told (Hasan, 2013),

"We welcome guests, but don't want Bandarban to become crowded or polluted like Rangamati. We don't want to lose our culture nor see it consigned to a museum."

Study Objectives:

Primary Objectives of the Survey:

To develop a Community-based Ecotourism Development Plan for Tanguar Haor, that will ensure-

- Sustainable Economic Contribution to the Local Communities
- Conservation and Sustainable Management of Natural Resources of TH

Methodology:

Timing of the survey: The study team, along with the IUCN officials visited the Tanguar haor from 15 to 18 March, 2015. This was the transition period for Tanguar haor from winter to pre-monsoon. Therefore it was easier for the team to move around the whole area on three wheeler, motor bikes, country boats and speed boats.

We along with the officials of IUCN, had visited Tanguar Haor from 16 -18 March, 2015. This is dry season and we had to avail a combination of different types of transports and vehicles to have a circuitous tour at Tanguar haor. The vehicles included three wheelers, motor bikes, speed boats, rowing country boats, and walking indeed. The route was as follows:

1. From Sunamgonj to Solaimanpur : by three wheelers, mechanized country boats and walking
2. Solaimanpur to Golabari : by speed boast
3. Golabari to Hatirgata : by rowing country boats
4. Hatirgata to Bagalvita : by motor bikes
5. Bangalvita to Jadukata river : by motor bikes
6. Jadukata rivar to Sunamgonj: mechanized boat, motor bikes, and three wheelers.

Methodology of the survey: Mainly Observation method and face-to-face discussions with the common people and the stake holders were employed. Beside, a Focus Group discussion was arranged at Banaglvida where the team had the opportunity to discuss informally about the possibility of introducing tourism there and ways to involve the local communities.

The team talked with several individual persons which include shop keepers, motor bike drivers cum owners, three wheeler drivers, boat rowers, NGO people, villagers, guides, IUCN officials and others.

In the FGD at Bangalvita, the Chairman of the Management Committee of that union and 30 to 35 people were present. The team also had the opportunity to talk with some of the village women at Bangal vita.

Tourism in Tanguar Haor: Although there has been no statistics available on the tourist arrival in that area, it has been reported around 8 to 10 thousands tourists visit this wetland every year. Majority of the tourists are researchers and bird watchers. Quite a negligible portion of the tourists visit the haor just for recreation. Uniqueness of Tanguar haor tourism is that it has two seasons : winter and monsoon. The local people reported that the ratio of tourists as per winter and monsoon seasons is almost 7:3.

Tanguar haor is situated just at the foot of long stretched Khasi hills of Meghalaya state of India. The natural beauty, unique biodiversity of plants and animals make Tanguar haor an ideal place for wanderlust and Sunlust tourism. It also is a worthy place for researching flora and fauna. Hundreds of ornithologists, bird watchers, and photographers visit the haor every year.

The under-construction road from Sunamganj to Kalmakanda of Netrokona district which goes just through the elongated Khasi foothills of Meghalaya state of India and the enormous crystal blue waters of Tanguar haor will make the area a hub tourism in future with a different flavour and attire. It will happen even if we want it or not.

Chapter 2

Situational Analysis of Tanguar Haor

Demography and poverty of Local people

Tanguar Haor is one of the largest wetland ecosystems in northeast region of Bangladesh comprising of 10,000 ha or 100 sq. km of land area. Administratively, within the total area of Tanguar Haor there are two sub-districts of Sunamganj district e.g. Tahirpur and Dharmapasha and four unions e.g. Uttar Bangshikunda, Dakshin Bangshikunada, Uttar Sreepur, Dakshin Sreepur. About 50% of the area (5,682 ha) of Tanguar haor is water bodies, followed by 31% crop land (Phase I Completion Report, IUCN 2010).

As it has already been mentioned earlier that Tanguar haor itself a unique waterbody, the ecosystem of which supports nearly 200 species of wetland flora, 141 species of fish (half of the total freshwater fish species found in Bangladesh), 11 amphibians, 34 reptiles and 208 species of birds of which 98 are migratory (IUCN, 2010). The ecological system surrounding Tanguar Haor provides livelihood to some 77,000 people spread over 88 villages.

Socio-Economic Profile of the Tanguar Haor Area

Wetland ecosystems are of great importance to Bangladesh due to their extent and of the critical economic and ecological role that they play in sustaining life and livelihoods in the country (Sobhan et al., 2012). Most economic activities carried out in the area, including commercial fishing, trade in fuel wood, hunting and trapping waterfowl, harvesting and sale of grasses and reeds and farming is based on wetland resources. The following Table shows the involvement of local community in different economic activities.

Table 1: Involvement of local community in different occupation (economic activities)

Occupation	In %
Agriculture	36.3
Fishing	41.7
Handicraft	1.5
Small business	10.4
Livestock	10.1
Total	100

Source: adapted from IUCN publication, June 2013

However, presently the economic activities have been diversified to some extent covering sand, pebbles and coal collection, guiding, boating etc.

However, fishing and farming are the principal occupations of people living in Tanguar Haor and of these two major economic activities, fishing and fish related activities are predominant. Table 2 shows the percentage of households engaged in varieties of fishing activities at Tanguar haor.

Table 2: Type of involvement in fishing activities

Type of involvement	Percent of HH
Fish catch	55.5
Fish business (wholesale)	3.9
Fish business (retail)	21.6
Boatmen	6
Fishing labour	1.9
Others (trap making and selling, fish drying, ice selling etc)	11.1
Total	100

Source: Adapted from IUCN Survey, 2008 (cited by Sobhan et al., 2012)

It is clear from the table that occupational status is largely depend on fish resources and people of Tanguar Haor are becoming more and more engaged in fishing than ever before.

Poverty level of the communities

The extent of poverty varies from one area to another area of Tanguar haor depending upon access to resources and the proximity from the main economic zones. Most of the people have a struggling economic life and their per capita income is also much less. We have compiled the following table to have a glimpse on their earning capability on some selected villages from a study by IUCN :

Name of the Village	Income (monthly in Taka	Main occupation	Others
Joypur	3000 - 5000	Fishing, boat owning, farming, seasonal labor	No work in monsoon. Transport is big problem
Jayosree	3000 - 10000	Fishing, farming	No work in monsoon.
Lama Gao	2000 - 5000	Fishing, farming, and boat owning	No work in monsoon.

Ramshingpur	± 4500	Farming, fishing	No work in monsoon. 50% of the population migrate to cities for odd jobs.
Mujrai	4000 - 6000	Farming, fishing, boat owning,	No work in monsoon.
Patapuka	500 -1200	Fishing, restricted farming	No work in monsoon.
Antarapur	5000 – 7000	Fishing, farming, day labor	No work in monsoon.
Nobabpur	±3000	Farming	No work in monsoon.
Rongchi	±6000	Farming	No work in monsoon.

Source: Compiled from the study on DRR: A Case Study of Tanguar Haor, IUCN,B. 2011

It seems from the above facts and figures that the whole population of Tanguar haor is solely dependent on fishing and farming as their main lively hood earning. During monsoon these people do not have any other significant alternative earning sources by which they can support their families. So they migrate to nearby towns and cities like Sunamganj, Habiganj, Sylhet, and even far to Dhaka, Chittagong, Comilla in search of odd jobs. This situation clearly indicates economic vulnerability of the local people. Consequently, they have to have become more dependent on the Haor itself creating a long term negative impact on the balanced ecology and biodiversity of the beautiful haor.

Considering these findings, it becomes quite clear that the policy makers and the stakeholders immediately try to identify alternative earning sources for these poor communities. In an effort to supplement their income both in the winter and in monsoon, creation of some tourism services and facilities could be valuable and worthwhile.

Tourism as an Economic Activity:

We have already mentioned earlier that we do not have any statistics available on the tourist arrival in that area. However, it has been reported by the local people, the local administration and the NGO people that **around** 8 to 10 thousands tourists visit this wetland every year. It has also been reported that majority of the tourists are researchers and bird watchers. Quite a negligible portion of the tourists visit the haor just for recreation. Uniqueness of Tanguar haor tourism is that it has two seasons: winter and monsoon. Majority of the tourists visit Tanguar haor during winter season with a prime objective to watch birds. The local people reported that the ratio of tourists as per winter and monsoon seasons is almost 7:3. Majority of the tourists come to Tanguar haor just for a day long visit as there has been no infrastructure developed to accommodate the tourists for their overnight stay. Consequently major part of the tourist money is being spent in Sunamganj town. In a rough estimation, only around 16 million tourist taka is retained in Tanguar haor in a year. If some eco-friendly infrastructure for accommodation, food and safety and security can be arranged, the tourist night can be extended remarkably which in turn will increase income of the local community by engaging them in different tourist services and activities like supply of accommodation,

food, and drinks. Scope for other added services like boating, guiding, watching birds, fish, plants etc. could be explored in a most integrated way by keeping in mind the sensitive biodiversity issues.

Contributions of IUCN in Protecting Tanguar Haor :

In 2000, the Ministry of Environment and Forests designed and developed a 'Tanguar Haor Management Plan with the support of IUCN, Bangladesh. The IUCN helped to design the Project Proposal. In 2005 a tripartite agreement was signed among MoEF, Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), and IUCN for funding arrangements. And in December 2006, Community Based Sustainable Management of Tanguar Haor (CBSMTH) project was launched (adapted from 'Final Fact Sheet TH, 2015).

Project phase 1 was preparatory and the duration was almost 2.5 years (December, 2006 to April, 2009). The objectives of the phase 1 were :

1. Selected communities of Tanguar Haor have capacity and organization to participate in pilot co-management activities
2. Institutional system is developed and piloted to support towards the development of a fully operational co-management system for Tanguar Haor
3. Knowledge on Tanguar Haor is organized to provide necessary input for the development phase.

The achievements of this phase of the project were :

1. Formed committee at village, union & central level.
2. Conducted resource inventory and prepared resource map.
3. Notification of Tanguar Haor Management Committee (THMC).
4. Joint patrolling.
5. Resource Sharing modality developed.

After the end of the 1st Phase of the project, the Second Phase started in May, 2009 and continued up to June, 2012. The 1st phase was mobilization stage and IUCN was fully equipped with the ground work and base line data and information which gave clear direction about the huge task of protecting the haor in one hand, and on the other hand to mobilize the local population under some structured form of organization.

The broad objective of the 2nd phase was to establish a co-management system for conservation, stabilization and sustainable use of the natural resources of Tanguar Haor that would generate opportunities for improving the livelihood of the communities and also contribute to the costs incurred by management.

The Specific objectives were :

1. A community based management system is established for conservation and sustainable use of natural resources of Tanguar Haor.
2. A sustainable co-management body composed of the state, local government and communities manages the Tanguar Haor.

3. Opportunities have been generated for significant improvements in the livelihoods of communities around Tanguar Haor.

The achievements after the end of the 2nd phase were tremendous which reflect the success stories of IUCN in mobilizing the local people and increasing their livelihood. These achievements in nutshell are :

1. A co-management model established.
2. Consolidation of Social Capital Management accumulated 1.38 BDT. crore.
3. Livelihood improvement interventions-28 types of AIGs practiced.
4. Five fish sanctuaries with 19 hotspots established.

The 3rd phase started in July 2012 and is supposed to finish in June 2015. This phase may be termed as the Consolidation stage and the broad objectives were :

Developing a well groomed co-management system to conserve ecosystem and natural resources, and turning it into a supporting and decision making platform for improving the livelihood of the communities.

Specific objectives:

1. The co-management system in Tanguar haor is consolidated and effective.
2. The communities of the Tanguar haor have improved their livelihoods and increase income.
3. The sustainability is assured beyond the project intervention.

Achievements:

1. Core and Buffer Zone demarcated.
2. 1,30,000 natural fingerlings restocked.
3. Completed Registration of TH Samajvittik Sahobybasthapona Society.
4. Gazette notification of National Scientific Body.
5. Formation of National Wetland Network.
6. Established 2 Bird Sanctuary and 2 artificial nests for threatened Pallas's Eagle.
7. Plantation of 4.6 ha Hijal & Koroch species for biodiversity conservation.

In Addition, IUCN published more than 10 research and survey papers and reports on Tanguar haor, and a number of leaflets ,fliers, and booklets to depict the endless resources of Tanguar haor which in turn worked as the promotional materials to publicise Tanguar haor.

IUCN is working successfully in protecting many of the wetlands in many countries of the world. In Bangladesh too they are working effectively to protect Tanguar haor and the success of this endeavor resulted in protecting a RAMSAR site from undeniable ruination.

Till the end of the 3rd phase, the project has been operating its activities through 73 Village, 4 Union and 1 Central co-management organizations. It successfully introduced Livelihood Improvement Plan (LIP) and facilitated to form participatory community based Social Capital Management (SCM) fund which is assisting Alternative Income Generating Activities (AIGAs) leading to raised livelihood. The project's motivational campaign imbued the idea in the

minds of the people about the importance of biodiversity conservation. The Project has so far introduced 5 fish and 2 bird sanctuaries. Community gets Monitoring and Evaluation training on biodiversity conservation.

Community has its own resource protection force – Community Guard. Government is actively considering supporting this force. On the other hand, Executive Magistrates with the support of law enforcing agencies are protecting resources of Tanguar Haor round the year. In lean period, fishermen community receives VGF support from Government.

With the above mentioned success and support from Government, IUCN is working on to formulate a unique organization-Tanguar Haor Management Authority (THMA) as a technical support organ for the co-management organizations.

The endeavour of IUCN, like any other place, has been successful. But the main focus was on biodiversity conservation and improving the livelihood of the community there. However, now a recent phenomenon of involving the community people to protect their assets they own entails the importance of introducing the concept of community based tourism – the proposition which creates the sense of ownership of the tourism assets surrounding them and capitalizing the asset in supplementing their income by offering tourism services to the visitors. Community based tourism easily can be introduced in Tanguar haor as it already is having a reputation as a touristic place specially in the winter season. At present almost 8 to 10 thousand tourists visit Tanguar haor each year. These visitors knowingly or unknowingly, are contributing towards degradation of the biodiversity and ecological aspects of Tanguar haor. To minimize this threat, it has been mandatory to go for experimenting the opportunity for introducing Community based tourism in Tanguar haor. Realizing this reality, the IUCN-B has initiated the present study on feasibility of introducing community based tourism in Tanguar haor.

Chapter 3

Political and Legal Environment Regulating Tourism Development

Absence of specific law and policy to protect Wetlands:

Our constitution (Section 18A) has recognized the importance of water resources in the life and economy of Bangladesh and the conservation of environment in the following manner: “The state shall endeavour to protect and improve the environment and to preserve and safeguard the natural resource, bio-diversity, wetland, forests and wild life for the present and future citizens.”

We also adopted the international treaty of RAMSAR Convention on Wetlands on 21st September, 1992.

All these indicate that wetlands (haor, baor, bils, jalmahal, ponds, sea-shore, etc.) have drawn attention of our policy makers. Still, for reasons unknown, in our country we do not have any specific policy and law regarding wetland, its use, management etc.

In Bangladesh, there are some policies and laws in relation to environment protection, water policy, ‘Jalmahal’ management, coastal zone, national park, wild life sanctuaries, agriculture and land policy etc. where some sections or clauses regarding various dimensions of wetlands have been incorporated. These laws are (Alam) :

1. Bangladesh Water Act 2013
2. National River Protection Commission 2013
3. Mega city, Divisional Town and District Town’s municipal areas including country’s all the municipal areas’ playground, open space, park and natural water reservoir Conservation Act, 2000 and natural water reservoir Conservation Act, 2000
4. The Canal Act 1864 ,
5. Bangladesh Environment Protection Act 1995
6. Local Government (Pourashava) Act 2009 ,
7. Local Government (City Corporation) Act 2009 ,
8. Local Government (Union Parishad) Act
9. Game Reserve, National Park and Wildlife Sanctuary as declared under the Bangladesh Wild Life (Preservation) Order, 1973; and
10. Ecologically Critical Areas (ECA) notified under the Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act, 1995.

In some of the laws much has been mentioned about the wildlife sanctuaries, but nothing (or very negligible) has been mentioned specifically about the wetlands.

The Bangladesh Wild Life (Preservation) Order, 1973 (President’s Order 23 of 1973), for example, was the first comprehensive legislation for control and management of wild animals

including its habitat. This law clearly defined a 'wild life sanctuary' and elaborated prohibitions thereto (Rahman, 2005) as follows:

As per Article 2(p) "Wild Life Sanctuary" means an area closed to hunting, shooting or trapping of wild animals and declared as such under article 23 by the Government as undisturbed breeding ground primarily for the protection of wild life inclusive of all natural resources, such as vegetation, soil and water."

As per the Article 23. **(1), The Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, declare any area to be wild life sanctuary.**

(2) No person shall –

- (i) enter or reside in any wild life sanctuary ; or
- (ii) cultivate any land in any wild life sanctuary ; or
- (iii) damage or destroy any vegetation in any wild life sanctuary ; or
- (iv) hunt, kill or capture any wild animal in any wild life sanctuary or within one mile from the boundaries of a wild life sanctuary ; or
- (v) introduce any exotic species of any animal into a wild life sanctuary ; or
- (vi) introduce any domestic animal or allow any domestic animal to stray into a wild life sanctuary ; or
- (vii) cause any fire in a wild life sanctuary ; or
- (viii) pollute water flowing in or through a wild life sanctuary : Provided that Government may, for scientific purposes or for aesthetic enjoyment or betterment of scenery, relax all or any of the prohibitions specified above.

(3) The Government may declare any area to be a national park where the following acts shall not be allowed, namely –

- (i) hunting, killing or capturing any wild animal in a national park and within the radius of one mile outside its boundary ;
- (ii) firing any gun or doing any other act which may disturb any wild animal or doing any act which may interfere with the breeding places of any wild animal ;
- (iii) feeling, tapping, burning or in any way damaging or destroying taking, collecting or removing any plant or tree therefrom ;
- (iv) clearing or breaking up any land for cultivation, mining or for any other purpose ;
- (v) polluting water flowing in and through the national park : Provided that the Government may, for scientific purposes or for betterment of the national park or for aesthetic enjoyment of scenery or for any other exceptional reasons, relax all or any of the prohibitions specified above.

However, in the Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act 1995, section 5, the Government has declared some wetlands of the country as ecologically critical Areas (ECA) for the protection of natural environment and sustainable environmental management, for example, St. Martin's Island, Hakaluki Haor, Tanguar Haor, Marjat Baor and Gulshan-Baridhara Lake. All activities that may deteriorate the environment further are prohibited in these areas (DoE 2002).

Beside, Bangladesh is a signatory to some international conventions (Islam 1996), which have bearing on protected areas. These conventions are:

1. Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). The purpose of CITES is to protect certain endangered species from over-exploitation by means of a system of import and export control.
2. Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage. The purpose is to establish an effective system of collective protection of the cultural and natural heritage of outstanding universe value, organized on a permanent basis and in accordance with modern scientific methods.
3. International Plant Protection Convention. The objective is to maintain and increase international cooperation in controlling pests and diseases of plants and plant products, and in preventing their introduction and spread across national boundaries.
4. Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat (Ramsar Convention) to stem the progressive encroachment on and loss of wetlands now and in the future, recognizing the fundamental ecological functions of wetlands and their economic, cultural, scientific and recreational value.
5. Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) to conserve biological diversity, promote the sustainable use of its components, and encourage equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources.

On the other hand, Bangladesh has the following major laws and Acts in the area of Tourism and related sectors :

1. The Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (BPC) Order – 1972 (Bangladesh Tourism Corporation)
2. The Bangladesh Parjatan Board Law – 2010. (Bangladesh Tourism Board)
3. The Bangladesh Reserved Area Tourism Law – 2010
4. Bangladesh Hotel and Restaurant Law -2013
5. Besamarik Biman Chalachal Kortripoksho Ain (Civil Aviation Authority Act) - 2013
6. Bangladesh Travel Agency (Registration and Control) Act -2013

However, in any of the laws and Acts nothing has been mentioned about the wetland tourism, conservation of the biodiversity of wet lands, water preservation and management etc. So in view of the ever growing demand for the wetland tourism in Bangladesh we need to have laws immediately to protect these wetland (haor, baor, beel, coastal zones and beaches etc.).

While formulating the laws in relation to wetland tourism, the following points may be important to keep in consideration :

1. **Reducing the negative impact of developments and tourist infrastructures on wetlands**
2. **Reducing consumption of natural resources and the pollution caused by tourist activities**
3. ***Controlling the development of tourist activities affecting the wetland (and also coastal) environment***

These points are being discussed in detail in the following paragraphs :

(1) Reducing the negative impact of developments and tourist infrastructures on wetlands:

Wetlands - especially the protected ones - are a tourist attraction and when their recreational use is not strictly regulated and monitored it can cause negative impacts on species dwelling in the area. Uncontrolled development of infrastructures and tourist related urbanization (especially, tourist accommodation, transports, eating places) can lead to irreversible deterioration of ecosystems.

Kusler (2006) proposed the following measures to reduce the negative impacts (with some modifications):

- acquire the instruments needed to evaluate the environmental impact of tourist programmes and large-scale projects,
- carry out evaluations of destination sites' carrying capacity and taking steps necessary for ensuring that the offer be limited to the carrying capacities thus defined,
- strengthen or establish legislative tools, regulations and property management leading to controlling urbanization and protecting the most precious natural sites.
- avoiding generalized urbanization too close to wetlands/coastlines and the building of roads parallel and close to wetlands/ coastlines that promote this kind of urbanization and generate traffic that alters the quality of the destination areas,

(2) Reducing consumption of natural resources and the pollution caused by tourist activities :

Tourism causes heavy consumption of natural resources (especially water, soil and energy) and produces a lot of waste. This consumption and waste production is added to those generated by the local population. These effects are very serious.

Some basic guidelines in achieving this goal as given by Kusler (2006) are presented below with some modifications:

- ensuring good environmental management of tourist facilities in destination sites
- encouraging quality environmental procedures
- developing all means that may lead to extending the tourist season over the entire year
- promote the tourist sector:
 - to fight against waste and pollution (reduced consumption, purification and recycling), energy waste (energy savings and use of renewable energy, especially solar energy) and waste (minimization, selective collection, recycling, etc.)
 - to promote clean and innovative technology
 - to develop voluntary tools such as environmental charters.

(3) Controlling the development of tourist activities affecting the wetland (and also coastal) environment :

Development of boating and some new water based leisure activities and underwater tourism can seriously affect the environment and certain protected species. In order to mitigate these impacts the local authorities should take the necessary steps so that:

- leisure boats do not discharge their waste water at anchors,
- harbors be furnished with the necessary facilities for taking solid and liquid waste,
- new leisure forms likely to affect the environment, especially protected species, only be authorized once their impact has been assessed and are shown to conform to the tourist strategies of the areas concerned,
- access and use of wetland area by the public be regulated and managed in accordance with environmental factors.

Last of all, in formulating the laws regarding the protection and management of wetlands, the roles of local stakeholders, guides, and the tour operators must be given due weightage. Individual tourists are more responsible for biodiversity degradation than tourists coming in groups. Because the group tourism is conducted by the tour operators; and the operators train up the tourists on the “dos and don’ts” activities and also ensure watchful monitoring system on the activities.

Chapter 4

Existing Tourism and Structure of Tourism industry

Attractions for tourists

The whole haor area itself is the tourist attraction for its unique characteristics and unparalleled natural setting that cannot be found in any traditionally well-known destinations in Bangladesh. For those who did never even imagine of a boating in a sea-like water where they can see by their own eyes different species of fishes swimming in the crystal clear water while thousands of birds flying over their heads, Tanguar Haor just can be a destination of 'out of this world'. This is a 'not for all' destination where only those are welcomed to explore the heavenly natural setting who have the courage to undergo all the troubles of the journey. Nature is in a very original stage there that attracts those who don't worry about facilities and services but love to roam around the nature.

The haor decorates itself in two different miens in two different seasons- winter and monsoon. For many, winter is the best time to visit Tanguar Haor as it was found from the field visit that more than two-third of the tourists choose winter for exploring Tanguar Haor.

Tourism Attractions of Tanguar Haor in Winter: Every winter Tanguar Haor attracts hundred thousands of migratory birds to visit it and spend their winter there. As a result, bird-lovers and photographers follow the flock and find themselves in Tanguar Haor. Migratory birds start to come in Tanguar Haor in October, thus winter tourism also starts in October and continues till the end of March every year. Prior to these during October/November and at the later part during February/March the weather is intermittently cold. The temperatures during this period range between 8.5 and 16.6 degree Celsius (IUCN, 2011). In November, leeves or kandas (banks or higher grounds between the *beels*) start to come out of the water that were waterlogged during rainy season. These leeves or kandas remain dry till the early rains in April and during this period these lands become the naturally made garden of different wetland related plants that create an unbelievably magnificent picture. Tourists can enjoy the haor not only by boating around it, but they can also walk through different leeves or kandas to feel them inside the nature in winter.

Tourism Attractions of Tanguar Haor in Monsoon: In monsoon, Tanguar haor looks as if an endless sea comprising all the beels and even the rivers across the haor area. Though monsoon or the rainy season extends from June to September with 80% of the annual rainfall during this period, it starts to rain early in April. All the leeves or kandas goes under water this time and only the villages in the relatively high land can manage to remain dry but like isolated island in the endless sea. Adventure lovers, who have their dream to boat in a sea-like water body under the clouded sky that rains unpredictably, will certainly choose monsoon to visit Tanguar Haor. Monsoon brings the opportunity for the mindful tourists to observe the hardship of life of the local people living in the isolated island-like villages and working under the hard rain for livelihoods. The Hijol-Korocho (*Barringtonia acutangula* and *Pongamia*

pinnata) trees can be found creeping their heads from water during rainy season that creates an unforgettable experience for lifetime.

In addition to these unparalleled seasonal appearances of natural beauty, the haor possesses something more for tourists regardless of the season they visit it. Tanguar haor is the home for wetland plants, different species of freshwater fishes, thousands of resident and migratory birds, and other wildlife. For nature lovers, zoologists, researchers and curious minds the haor is one of the best place to observe all in one place.

The farfetched view of layers of high hills in the Indian part from Tekerhat point, the sandy Jadukata River and its origin, the view of sandy and stony river banks from Barikkar Tila and Laurer Gohr can make anyone forget the hustle and bustle of their routine life.

In Bangal Vita there are ethnic communities who are mainly Garo and Hazong. They have their own lifestyles including traditional dances, dresses, foods, and festivals. Garo people have their biggest festival called “Wangala” which is held in Bengali month of “Poush”. They have a special type of drink (alcohol) which is very special in nature.

There are also some other very interesting places around the haor where tourists can have a visit to. There is very old palace called “Week (wick) Razar Bari” situated in Chanpur Gaon near Barikkar Tila on the way to Jadukata River. Tourist can also find some handicrafts surround the village and those products are ‘kula’, ‘chalun’, ‘dhari’ etc. A village named Indrapur is famous for ‘Charak Punja’ among the ancient religion disciples, which is observed in April/May. During this festival thousands of devotees from India come to do their prayer.

Accommodation:

Hotels and rest houses of different ranges of facilities and prices are available in Sunamganj District Head Quarter. Though there is no hotel in Tahirpur Upazilla, a Government-owned Bungalow with only three rooms. In the main wetland starting from Golabari point, there is no formal provision for accommodation. The only place for tourists to stay at night is houseboat. But in Tanguar Haor, the number of houseboat is very limited and the facilities in the houseboat are not of that standard to satisfy all types of tourists. Houseboats serves tourists food services also where raw food items are reserved for two or three days of the total tour and then these are cooked and served inside the boat. For accommodation and food service for tourists, there is no better substitution for houseboats in Tanguar Haor yet and it can be the hot cake for tourists in future for ecotourism development if properly promoted.

Transportation:

Transportation system is not in an expected level there in Tanguar Haor from the points of view of both tourists and local people. As a result it is considered an equally remote area and a villager succinctly described the situation as, *“the villages of Tanguar are so remote that even news from the radio reaches a day later”* (Haque and Kazal, 2008).

Road transportation is useful in dry season. But the main transportation mode is water transportation regardless of season. Here is a table to show different routes within the Tanguar Haor area and the transports available. Prevailing costs of transportation are also shown in the table. The cost of transport of all modes apparently seems to be very high because of dilapidated condition of the roads, seasonality of movement, high maintenance cost, and limited number of transports available.

Table 3 : Different Routes within Tanguar Haor and Vehicle Available

Routes	Alternative Vehicles and Fares
Sunamgonj Sadar – Solaimanpur Ghat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three wheelers- BDT 1000, • Motor bike- BDT 400-500
Solaimanpur to Golabari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed boat (max. 10 persons)- BDT 7000, • Rowing country boats- BDT 1600-2000
Golabari to Hatirgata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rowing country boats- BDT 1500-2000
Hatirgata to Bagalvita	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motor bike- BDT 500
Bagalvita to Jadukata River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motor bike- BDT 450-500
To cross Jadukata River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boat- BDT 10 (per person)
Jadukata- Sunamgonj	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three wheelers- BDT 1000

Source : Field visit to Tanguar haor, March, 2015.

To develop the Tanguar Haor as an ecotourism destination, development in transportation sector is a must, but it must be eco-friendly.

Although winter is good for traveling at Haors, but its versatile beauty figured out individually at least in three different seasons : full monsoon, post monsoon, and winter. All these are having very different experiences. Especially, in rainy season it takes youthful and significant looks. Haors are flooded by the monsoon floods, and most retain some water throughout the dry season. In rainy its look like infinite water kingdom. Traveler enjoys a good time fully artificial free life with nature. It refreshes mind and body together.

Food and Beverage Facilities:

Though there are some restaurants in Sunamganj district town, there is no formal establishment for food and beverage services in Tanguar Haor. Establishing restaurant for tourists has not yet been profitable for the local people. Moreover, scarcity of land to establish a restaurant is another reason for that. The only provision for food for tourists is the food arrangement in the houseboats. Tourist groups that hire a houseboat for two or three days to roam around Tanguar Haor are provided with food in the houseboat for price. Beside, presently a big chunk of the tourists at Tanguar haor come for a single day. Consequently over-night stay and demand for food and water do not seem to be very important to the tourists. The tourists bring dry food and drink with them.

Handicrafts:

Local communities living in Tanguar Haor are not rich in handicraft. Only a few handicraft items are prominent. In Joypur a women made handbag for women which is basically made of plastic. Sheetal Pati, a special mat to cover floor made of skin of a specific plant called '*Mustak*', is made in Ganjail Gram. Boat is made in Noagaon, Uttiargaon. Different bamboo-made housewares like 'Kula', 'Chalun', 'Dhari' etc. are found in any village.

Tour Guiding:

IUCN trained 80 young people in tour guiding with a view to motivating them to take it as their profession. But, only a few of them have taken it as their permanent profession. IUCN tried to promote these individual tour guides by mentioning the contact details of these tour guides in their tour handbooks made for tourists. Presently, one of them has built a houseboat to operate in the haor for tourists.

Involvement of Tour Operators/Travel Agencies:

Tour operators and travel agencies have not yet found Tanguar Haor attractive enough to include in a package tour to offer to tourists. The main reason is the area's most undeveloped approachability through its submerged roads, muddy uneven field-strips, and finally the crisscrossed rivulets. The ground carriers are also not in good shape and condition. Beside, the lack of minimum services and facilities that the tourists normally expect, specially the tourists who do not want to take the donkeywork for travelling through still unspoilt natural setting, discourages the tour operators from planning and offering tour packages to Tanguar haor. It was found from the study that only the bird watchers, researchers, photographers, and the young adventure-loving university students consist the majority of tourists. This segment of tourists do not bother about the services and do not seek the services from tour operators and travel agencies. If the proper facilities for profitable customers/tourists can be developed, tour operators and travel agencies will be interested in Tanguar Haor.

Chapter 5

Tourism Strategies: Scope for CBT

A Short Description of CBT:

The term Community-based tourism holds the concept of offering tourism products to the tourists by communities with a view to meet economic, social, and environmental needs of local communities. Due to unprecedented growth of tourism and its negative effects, an increased interest has arisen in sustainable tourism and community-based tourism (CBT) (Shunnaq et al. 2008; Cooper 2004). Sustainable tourism and community-based tourism (CBT) are subsets of the concept sustainable development (UNWTO 2008 quoted by Braun). Sustainable development is defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) as 'development that meets that needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs' (WCED 1987). From the view point of CBT, sustainability may encompass economic, social, cultural, and environmental elements. A real CBT concept can bring sustainability in all these elements. Two prime concerns of sustainable tourism are (i) to increase the income of the local people (financial sustainability) and (ii) to conserve the tourism assets from destruction (environmental and ecological sustainability. Only a well-planned CBT effort can ensure these.

The catchy buzzword 'poverty reduction through tourism' is not meaningful in under developed/developing countries as the benefits of tourism as an economic activity may not reach up to the poor people. The African continent has experienced an exponential growth in the number of tourists, but this has not led to local communities obtaining economic, social or environmental benefits (Novelli and Gebhardt, 2007). It is postulated that if the members of a community become the owner of tourism assets, probably then they can rip the benefit of tourism. Keeping that in mind, for over three decades, CBT has been promoted as a means of development whereby the social, environmental and economic needs of the communities are met through the offering of tourism products they own.

Sustainability of the tourism assets, both natural and/or manmade, much depends on the extent of involvement of the community to protect it. Unless the community develops the feeling that tourism assets are the sources of income for them, these people will not be serious in caring and protecting the assets. Absence of government policies to involve the local community in maintaining and capitalizing the tourism assets is another major reasons of destruction.

Therefore, if we really mean sustainability of tourism assets, be it man-made or natural like Tanguar haor, Sundarban, picturesque Bandarban, St. Martin island etc. , there is no way but to involve the local community in money making activities capitalizing the attractions.

Involvement of the Community :

The term Community based tourism is a complex conception. Mere creation of tourism facilities and involving the local community in the tourism activities may not bring desired results. Here we can cite a unique example of this situation. Community-based tourism initiatives in Bolivia are based on the development of community-owned and managed lodges or homestays. At La Yunga the lodge, created by the donor agencies, attracted only 60 visitors per year with a bed occupancy of 2.7% only. Mere creation of lodges/homestays is not community based tourism. Tourists want prime tourism attractions. The common focus on accommodation only is inappropriate – the community rather benefited far more when it provided activities coupled with accommodation (Goodwin and Santilli).

The following three components are important to grasp an idea about a successful CBT initiative :

1. Tourism Attractions, man-made or natural
2. Community USTO (unique selling tourism offers – what the community has to offer to the tourists which is unique, entertaining, and attractive. Example may be the cultural performances of the tribal people.)

We get three models which show the interactive relationship among the three factors/components. The models are :

Model 1: Transit travelers destined for natural/man-made attractions via community settlements (main attraction is natural/man-made tourism assets; so less benefit to the community).

Model 2: Only Community USTOs (no other added natural attractions)

Model 3: Community USTOs blended with natural/man-made tourists attractions (community is the host)

Model 1 is not much appropriate for Tanguar haor as the attraction during winter is only bird watching. This single activity may not retain the tourists in the area more than a single day. Considering the biodiversity and ecological sensitivity of the area, there is very restricted scope for introducing other activities for the tourists especially in winter. The survey team could not identify some unique USTOs in the surrounding area excepting the possibility of turning the (till now) unpolished tribal cultural feats of the Garo and Hazong communities into some tourist products. So model 2 is not suitable for Tanguar haor.

However, if proper planning is formulated to explore and exploit some useful USTOs and tied up those with the natural uniqueness of Tanguar haor, it may be presumed that model 3 be useful for successful community based tourism development in the area.

Problem of involving communities in tourism activities at Tanguar haor :

Tanguar haor has natural attraction both in winter (bird watching) and in monsoon (huge wavy water reservoir). A small number of Garo and Hazong families inhabit in Banglavita, Bakatola, and Majhirschhara villages. However, these villages are almost impassable during winter season. Value tourists are supposed to remain confined only in the areas where they can watch birds and they may not be interested to take the trouble of motor biking a long uneven indigenous village strips to go to Bangalvita just to see the tribal cultural feats.

Strategic Application of the Models:

Out of three models it is obvious that in short term strategy formulation, model # 2 is not workable at Tanguar haor.

Model # 1 is doable with a limited scope during both the winter and monsoon slots. For value tourists model # 1 may not be possible, nevertheless we can encourage the adventure tourists to take the ordeal of motor biking to Bangalvita from Hatirgata. During winter time, some temporary accommodation may be created at Hatirgata for the adventure tourists with all precautions of not disturbing the ecological aspects of the area.

However, model # 3 has the chance to successful implementation during monsoon. During rainy season when Tanguar haor turns itself into a sea, tourists can easily go to Bangalvita tourism zone of Tanguar haor in two ways :

1. On house boats directly from Sunamgonj to Bangalvita and
2. On three wheelers or motor bikes, up to Tahirpur and from there on house boats directly to Bangalvita.

Therefore involvement of the local community may be ensured and encouraged by following Five ways :

- (a) Providing glass-roof very shallow draft silent electric boats to transport the tourist groups into the bird sanctuary.
- (b) Providing houseboats having facilities for sleep, eat, and toilet to the local (tourism) community management. Each house boats may have the carrying capacity of maximum 10 tourists.
- (c) Providing guide training to the young people of the community and making use of guides mandatory for all tourists. IUCN has already trained almost 80 young people in guiding.
- (d) Arranging the tribal cultural performances of the Garo and Hazong communities in such a way that it becomes a source of income for them
- (e) Experimentally a few number of community people may be trained up in catering, housekeeping and other hospitality activities for home-stay tourism at Golabari and Hatirgata (for winter tourists), Bangal vita, Bakatola (for monsoon tourists). But before that they should be financed to create separate good rooms with attached baths and ensure a hygienic environment for the plainland tourists.

In future, some of the community festivals like, Kali puza, Roth jatra, Shrabon Borto, Janmastomi, Chorok puza may be added to diversify the USTOs and also to make the tourists' prolonged stay there.

Observations from the Field Trip : Seasons for Haor Tourism :

We talked with several individual persons which include shop keepers, motor bike drivers cum owners, three wheeler drivers, boat rowers, NGO people, villagers, guides, IUCN officials and others.

We also had a FGD at Bangalvita where the Chairman of the Union Management Committee of that union and 30 to 35 people were present. We also talked with some of the village women at Bangal vita.

Tourist Seasons : After personal observations and assessment, discussion with the local stakeholders, we concluded that Tourism in Tanguar haor may comprise of two slots in a year:

1. Winter tourism
2. Monsoon tourism

Winter tourism mainly highlights bird watching and Monsoon tourism may feature huge wavy water kingdom in the lap of the hills of Meghalaya state of India. Accordingly we have proposed Two tourism Zones for separate niche markets.

Tourism Zones in Tanguar Haor : On the basis of two tourist seasons, we propose that there could be two tourist zones as follows.

Winter tourism : The zone will comprise of the destinations where bird watching will be main touristic activity. The zone may include Solaimanpur, Golabari, and Tanguar haor which includes Lechua (Leichher) beel, Rowa beel, Hatirgata beel, Rupabol beel, and other nearby water bodies.

Hatirgata shoal may be used as a centre point for the adventure tourists with makeshift arrangements for night stay, food, toilet etc.

Monsoon Tourism : During monsoon Tanguar haor takes a beautiful look - all plunged dip in water. Huge water reservoir gives a placid ,serene, and tranquil environment which is most suitable for sunlust type of tourism. Keeping this in mind we propose that the zone may comprise the destinations like Bangla vita, Bakatola, Majhirschhara, Indrapur, and other nearby inhabitations.

Maps of Zones and Routes :

Proposed Routes and Zone for Winter Tourism :

Winter Tourism : During winter till now there is no alternative route to reach to bird sanctuaries of Tanguar haor except the Solaimanpur – Golabari route. It may be shown as follows :

Map 1.1 : Proposed Route for Winter Tourism from Sunamganj and up to Solaimanpur ghat

The tourists have to come to Solaimanpur ghat via Bishwamvarpur and Tahirpur. From Solaimanpur ghat they have to hire water transport up to the point of Golabari. From Golabari the actual tourist zone will start. The main carrier in this zone will be house boats (boatels), indigenous boats etc.

Map 1.2 : The Actual Tourist Zone for Winter Tourism (up to Tanguar haor)

Golabari will be the main tourist point where the boats will be anchored. From Golabari the tourists can cover different beels for bird watching. If tourists want to spend night on the boats, Golabari will be the harbour for the house boats. Being nearer to the locality, Golabari enjoys advantages in terms of established backward linkage for getting supply of tourism services including safety and security.

For the adventure tourists, thatched makeshifts might be established at Hatir gata. Or, they may mount their tents there. It is, however, better that the local people arrange for the tents to house the tourists. From Hatir gata they can watch the birds and other species of animals. If they want, they can brave the arduous motor bike journey to Bangal vita – a tribal village. These bikes are driven by the local young people.

For the bird watchers and photographers, Golabari will be more convenient place to stay. The circuitous journey will start from here with some bigger boats. After sometime the tourists will have to shift to non-mechanized smaller boats accommodating 2-3 persons which will take them dip into the bird and fish sanctuaries. The one-day tourists will come back to Golabari and from there they can start for Sunamgonj via the same route. The visitors who decide to stay night in the haor, their house boat will be anchored at the Golabari point.

Proposed Routes and Zone for Monsoon Tourism :

Monsoon Tourism : During full-flood, the entire zone is inundated by huge water. Excepting the raised settlements, all the reeds, grass and other plants go under water. In some of the haors and beels within the territory of Tanguar haor like Chattania beel, Rupaboli beel and Tekunna beel, the inundated plants, for their survival, raise their tops above the water level serving the birds as their resting and nesting places. This scenic beauty in deep monsoon is unforgettable. Besides, during full-moon night, experience of boating through the huge pool of placid water coupled with tranquil environment gives a heaven-like feeling. At night the tourists can enjoy the tribal performances by the Garo and Hazong communities.

During monsoon, tourism route may be extended from Sunamganj to Bangal vita directly by boats specially made for accommodating the tourists in groups. The route may be shown as follows :

Map 2.1 : Route 1: All by boat (Sunamganj - Bangal Vita - Sunamganj)

After coming to Bangal vita, the tourists may stay nights in the boat, but if they want they can also avail homestay facility arranged and offered by the local people. For homestay facilities, some infrastructure should be developed for the plain land tourists. An extensive training program should be arranged for the local people for offering hospitality services to the tourists.

Map 2.2 : Route 2: Road and River Route through Tanguar Haor

As per the route number 2.2, the tourists may come by road from Sunamganj to Tahirpur. Then from Tahirpur the tourists can enjoy an exotic travelling experience by boathouses all through the sea-like Tanguar haor up to Bangal vita.

Map 2.3 : Tourist Rest Point (Anchorage of House Boats and Homestay for Tourists)

Proposed Long-term Tourism plan :

Long term tourism potentiality depends on the under construction road from Sunamganj to Netrokona which runs through a dreamy romantic environment of having huge blue water in one side and on the other side the picturesque Khasi hills range of India. However, main obstacle is Jadukata river where a big bridge is necessary to connect Sunamganj with Bangal vita via Taker haat. If it is completed, tourists will have an enjoyable journey from Sunamganj to haor areas of Netrokona with a stop over at Bangal vita or Barekkar Tila. Barekkar Tila is a beautiful small hillock where a resort can be established for the tourists. Barekkar Tila can be turned into an attractive tourist destination where from after a short drive the nature lovers can have a boat journey into the deep haor water. If ecologically it does not create any hazard, some watch towers and raised walking trails may be constructed at Hatirgata to provide tourists a natural view of the haor during monsoon. The local festivals like tribal dances and performances, Charak puza, Rothjatra, Shrabon borto, Garo and Hazong New year, Jonmashtomi etc. could be turned into unique selling tourism offers. In other words, there is ample scope for diversifying tourism activities within and around Tanguar haor in future. However, it needs further study to explore the scope for long term tourism there involving the local community.

Proposed Long-term Tourism Route:

Map 3.1 : Proposed Long-term Route for Tourism starting from Sunamganj and up to Bridge (proposed) over the Jadukata River

Map 3.2 : Proposed Long-term Route through Tekerhat Road connecting the bank of Jadukata River and Bangal Vita

Map 3.3 : The Long-term Tourist Zone (up to Tanguar Haor)

Tourism Strategy Involving the Local People

Further study is needed to identify the ways of involving the local community in different tourist activities. Haors, being very sensitive areas, require much more experimentation to finally decide on the ways of involving the local community. However, in the following sections we would try to identify, from the field experiences, some probable ways to involve the local community specifically in tourism activities.

Winter Tourism :

Actors :
Guides
Boatmen
Cooks
Helping hands

Logistics :
Boats (*larger boats for night stay, small boats for roaming around to watch birds*)
Food and water
Daily necessities
Tents for night stay at Hatirgata.
Makeshift arrangements for kitchen, toilet etc. at Hatirgata
Waste disposal facilities

Management : MoEF and IUCN created village based Tanguar haor Management Committee

Monsoon Tourism :

Actors : Boatmen (larger boats for night stay)
 Guides
 Local Tribal people
 Home stay providers
 Cooks
 Helping hands
 Small shopkeepers
 Tribal performers and Trainers

Logistics : Larger Boats(boatels)
 Food and water
 Daily necessities
 Waste disposal facilities

Management : MoEF and IUCN created village based Tanguar haor Management Committee.

The union level MoEF and IUCN created Tanguar haor Management Committee will determine which of the villages and the inhabitants could be involved in tourism related activities. They will decide how many larger boats and smaller boats may be required to ferry the tourists. Finally they will also decide on the number and involvement of the local people who would carry on the tourist activities. MoEF and IUCN , along with other NGOs and donor agencies, will train up the local people, and also help getting the funds for suitable liveable boatels and small ferrying boats for bird watching.

Facilities and services required :

Tanguar haor, in true sense, does not have any infrastructure to meet the needs of the tourist. Near Golabari, the Forest department has built a beautiful watch tower to view the birds. Creation of such small infrastructure can, if properly sited and designed, both meet the needs of ecotourists while protecting natural resources (Kusler,2006). These small eco-friendly facilities, under close surveillance, will make the tourists disciplined and aware about the importance of preserving the ecology and biodiversity. The facilities include wetland trails adjacent to wetlands, boardwalks, signs, and boat launching areas. They also include information centers, and food and lodging facilities on adjacent lands, if properly sited and constructed.

Some common types of educational and interpretative materials include:

- Trail guides at strategic points along a trail or boardwalk
- Wetland maps
- Interpretative signs
- Bird lists
- Fact sheets and interpretative pamphlets
- Recorded and live lectures, and
- Guided walks, boat tours

Eco friendly vehicles :

(i) Shallow draft silent boats for Winter Tourism : The main mode of transport in and around Tanguar haor is boat dependent. However, these boats are engine –run indigenous boats making huge noise pollution and water pollution through spillage of fuel and lubricant. As alternative way, during the winter and monsoon seasons, 50 seater glass roof very shallow draft (50 cm draft) silent electric boats bought secondhand from Amsterdam, Holland can be operated to take the tourists to the deeper haor areas, including the bird sanctuary. These boats are absolutely safe to carry the tourists and also environment friendly as these are driven by electric power hence create no sound pollution to disturb the birds. Beside, chance of oil and lubricant spillage and CO₂ emission is nil.

Picture 1: 50 seater glass roof shallow draft (50 cm) silent electric Canal Boat

Source : from internet.

Some smaller pedal/engine boats for 4 – 6 persons resembling the Swans may also be procured and deployed in winter season to cater the needs of tourists who want to have fun. Following is a picture of such type of beautiful looking swan-boats to carry the tourists in the Hun river of Seoul, South Korea :

Picture : 1.1 : Swan-boats at the anchorage

Photo by the author

Picture 1.2 : Swan-boats carrying the tourists

Photo by the author

(ii) HOUSEBOATS the Paradise on Waves for Monsoon Tourism :

Houseboats are huge, slow-moving barges used for leisure trips. Such a houseboat is about 60 to 80 feet (18 to 23 m) long and about 15 feet (4.6 m) wide at the middle. The hull is made of wooden planks. Use of houseboats is quite an old tradition in the Indian subcontinent. Mughal emperor Humayun used to enjoy river cruising with the houseboat. In Kashmir, along famous Dal lake hundreds of houseboats are seen and some of them more than 100 years old. Kerala tourism has flourished because of so many factors, house boat is one of these. The houseboats may be of different sizes, some having up to three bedrooms apart from a living room and kitchen. House boats normally carry 8 to 12 persons.

Like hotels, houseboats vary in degree of luxury. A luxury houseboat, like a luxury hotel has fine furniture, good carpets and modern bathroom fittings, the lowest category of houseboats, like low-budget hotels, is spartanly furnished. All houseboats, regardless of category, have highly personalized service. In order to offer services to the tourists, each houseboat employ "houseboys". Every standard houseboat provides a balcony in the front, a lounge, dining room, pantry and 3 or more bedrooms with attached bathrooms. Some model houseboats can be seen below which ply mainly in Kerala :

Cost of these houseboats in Kerala varied from 6,00,000 to 30,00,000 Indian Rupees depending on the category of engines used, services and amenities provided, and the materials used in building the structure (indialandmart.com, retrieved May, 2015).

Role of the Tour Operators :

When the question of highly sensitive protective issues come up for a particular destination, it become almost mandatory to involve the expert Tour Operators to conduct the tour program for the tourists in groups. For this type of highly sensitive destinations, it is advisable not to encourage private tours, be it individual or groups.

The Tour Operators are well trained and oriented to conduct tour programs to these places where they put maximum endeavour to maintain the ecological balance, they train up the tourists, remain alert for any damaging activities knowingly or unknowingly done by the tourists.

For Tanguar Haor, a panel of solvent and experienced Tour Operators may be developed. These tour operators will need permission from the Ministry of Environment and Forests at a nominal fee. A code of conduct may be developed for these Tour Operators. The UNWTO has put so much importance on the role of the tour operators that in their charter it was mentioned how **tourism businesses can promote and support wetland biodiversity. The six-point charter was as follows :**

- reducing pollution from tourism activities, particularly by ensuring that all liquid and solid wastes are properly treated and disposed of in ways that do not result in damaging biodiversity,
- obtaining all food stuffs, and other biological resources used in tourism activities, from sustainably managed sources;
- supporting biodiversity conservation by government agencies and NGOs through practical actions, including financial contributions,
- ensuring that no invasive alien species are introduced through tourism activities;
- ensuring that no threatened or endangered species are put at risk from tourism activities or enter the tourism supply chain (especially as foods or souvenirs); and
- using the communications and marketing strengths of the tourism sector to raise awareness of tourists and destination authorities of the value of biodiversity and the steps they can take to protect it.

Raising fund to protect the Haor :

Protecting wetland biodiversity is not only government's responsibility. The stakeholders and the beneficiaries including the tourists shall also participate in this process. This is a huge and expensive job. In order to protect the biodiversity of haors, government, local government, local informal administration, local individual people, tour operators, and the tourists must come forward. As this process entails a fat amount of fund, a levy may be charged on each tourist entering into the haor area. This practice may help in making 'responsible tourists' in

one hand and restrict the number of unwanted tourists on the other hand. In addition, the collected fund may be utilized for protecting the ecology and biodiversity of haors. It is a practice worldwide for many of the most vulnerable tourist destinations.

Tourism Carrying Capacity :

Calculating Tourism Carrying Capacity (TCC) in a particular destination is an arduous job. TCC calculation entails three intricated facets : Physical Carrying Capacity (PCC), Real Carrying Capacity (RCC), and Effective Carrying Capacity (ECC). Physical, Real, and Effective carrying capacities should be addressed at the time of calculating TCC which was suggested by the IUCN (H. Ceballos-Lascuráin, 1996). Calculation of TCC for Tanguar haor is more complex because of its unique physical geography. It needs much more time to decide on the TCC figure. However, the present number of tourists as stated to be in and around the figure of 10,000 a year is not at all alarming. The real TCC should be calculated before a large number of tourists start rushing to Tanguar haor in near future.

Wetland conservation can only be achieved through a coordinated cooperative approach involving all levels of government and the public, NGOs, the private sector, and finally the community people.

Along with leisure and recreation, tourism educate the people in culture, nature history, and so many areas of civilization. This education program becomes more important when there is the issue of conservation. This is specifically true in case of wetland tourism. Continuously training up the tourists by developing some systems and structures like building the trail or boardwalk, erecting informative maps, bird list, pamphlets, guided tours etc. will enhance the awareness level of the tourists to protect the environment. For example, more than a million people may walk the Anhinga Trail in the Everglades (USA) each year. As they walk, they learn about wetlands and the importance of protecting such areas. This helps develop support for not only protecting the Everglades but also other wetlands in other areas (Sfougaris et al, 2009).

Chapter 6

SWOT and Value Chain Analyses : Involving the Government, NGOs and Development Partners with Tourism

This chapter examines the tourism related strength, weakness, opportunity and threat for the Tanguar haor. The SWOT analysis clearly identifies the need for introducing community based ecotourism in order to protect the biodiversity and ecological aspects of the haor in one hand and supplementing the earnings of the local people through tourism on the other hand.

SWOT analysis of tourism in Tanguar Haor

The reason of proposing the development of ecotourism in Tanguar Haor was based on the results of a SWOT analysis shown in the following Table :

Table 4 : SWOT analysis of ecotourism development in Tanguar Haor

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the most unique wetland eco-systems with unparalleled natural beauty that is entirely different from any other traditional destinations in Bangladesh. • A hosting place of most diverse and abundant flora and fauna including nearly 200 species of wetland vegetation, 141 species of fish, 11 amphibians, 34 reptiles. • One of the best places in Bangladesh to see nearly 208 different species of water birds of which 98 are migratory. • In 2000, it was declared the second RAMSAR site of Bangladesh highlighting its global importance. • It is listed in the Directory of Asian Wetlands (Scott, 1989). • Two different miens of natural beauty in two different seasons e.g. winter and monsoon. • Exotic boating routes through the sea-like water covering picturesque bird sanctuary and fish sanctuary. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seasonal pattern of tourism, that is, tourism occurs mainly in winter. No effort for exploring the potentiality of monsoon tourism. • Inadequate promotional efforts and lack of a brand identification. • Poor communities unable to invest in tourism (lack of initial investment funds) • Communities mostly unaware of ecotourism. • No infrastructure (accommodation, restaurant, shop, washroom) for tourism. • Scarcity of land needed for building tourist facilities. • Absence of houseboat concepts dedicated for tourists. • Lack of package tour programs by the tour operators because of poor transportation system to and within Tanguar Haor (both the road and water transportation systems).

<p>Lifestyle of local people and their island villages can also be observed closely from the boats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the largest domain of natural swamp forest. • Rich cultural environment and varied religious festivals of Garo and Hazong communities. • Tourism friendly local communities who are ready to accept tourists and take tourism as their supplementing livelihood. • Government and IUCN is working with commitment for tourism development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate trained/professional human resource for tourism services. • No plan and guidelines for tourism development. • Problems relating sanitary and hygiene all around the Tanguar Haor. • Lack of safety and security for tourists.
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecotourism in natural settings especially in wetland is a buzzword now among the local and international tourists. • Potential market/tourists for Tanguar Haor is increasing as domestic tourism is flourishing rapidly in Bangladesh. Adventure tourism is now very popular among young people in Bangladesh. • Establishment of Ecotourism projects/facilities can be initiated by different stakeholders with the support of Government and IUCN in near future. • Possible Public-Private-Community Participation (PPCP) approach for ecotourism development can make it a role model for community-based sustainable ecotourism development not only in Bangladesh but also in similar wetlands around the world. • Introducing comfortable houseboats (boatels) with good facilities can create huge demand for the wealthy sunlust tourists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential consumptive use of wetland resources for tourism development and catering the needs of tourists may pose a potential threat to the biodiversity and ecology. • Threat for ecological imbalance – including adverse effect on flora and fauna, swamp forest, beel and river – as a result of increased tourism development and influx of tourists . • Exploitation of local economy by private sector investors from outside. • Potential socio-cultural degradation as a result of huge influx of tourists. • Competition for land for tourism development purposes and local use. • Potential fear among local communities of losing the control over their territory and economy.

- Diverse backward and forward linkages of tourism will lead to more community involvement with more multiplier effect in tourism value chain.

From the above SWOT analysis it is evident that the development of community based ecotourism in Tanguar Haor enjoys more ‘strengths and opportunities’ than ‘weaknesses and threats’. The development of ecotourism involving the local community can be more effective for economic contribution to the local community as well as conservation of ecology and local culture than the present consumptive use of wetland resources that will ultimately lead to permanent degradation of natural and cultural resources.

Tourism Value Chain Analysis: Tanguar Haor

Why people visit Tanguar haor? As a tourist destination, it has been found that Tanguar haor is more popular for adventure type of tourism. Side by side Tanguar haor can be turned into a good destination for the people who want to have a relaxed time amidst Hill and water. However whatever is the motivation for tourism, the tourists need some basic facilities and services in the destination.

The tourism value chain in Tanguar haor generally integrates five main productive activities or sectors: accommodation, restaurants, transportation, handicrafts/shopping, and services like trekking, sightseeing etc.

Figure 2: Value Chain in tourism : Supply and Demand

The Overall tourism value chain in Tanguar Haor

The tourism value chain in Tanguar Haor generally integrates five main productive activities or sectors: accommodation, restaurants, transportation, handicrafts/shopping and tourism related services.

Figure 3: Overall tourism Value Chain with identified actors and activities at Tanguar haor.

After identifying the value chain activities, it becomes easier to identify who will do what. The factors of Value Chain are indicative, but on the basis of value chain, Action Plan Matrix is much more directive. The following is the Action Plan Matrix where the possible roles of the government, NGOs, and development partners have been examined :

**ACTION PLAN MATRIX: INTERVENTIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION
(As per Specific Value Chains/Activities)**

Value Chain/ Activities	Challenges for Tourism Development in Tangur Haor	Interventions	Time frame	Implementing Agencies
Accommodation, Food, and Water, and Utilities	Presently no Accommodation for the Tourists	* Needs to arrange eco-friendly accommodation especially on Boatels. * Helping local people to arrange for home-stay facilities.	Continuous but immediate to start	MoEF, IUCN, Financial Institutions, BUET (designing), Local Administration
	Crisis in Finance (small and Large)	Soft Loans	Short term and Long term	NGOs, Public and Private banks, MoEF, Ministry of Agriculture
	House Keeping Services	No knowledge. Training to local people in House keeping	Continuously for short and Long terms	BPC (NHTTI),
	No electricity supply	Needs intervention to generate electricity by installing Solar power devices	Short term and Long term	NGOs, MoEF, Development Partners, IUCN
	Availability of pure Water	Ensuring regular supply either by erecting tube wells or supply in jars/bottles	Immediately	Public Health & Engineering department, GoB, NGOs, IUCN, Local entrepreneurs
	No Food Supply/availability, Ensuring food quality and food safety	Training on food preparation, hygiene and law relating to food safety & restaurant	Immediately but should continue	BPC (NHTTI), NGOs, Local Administration
	No provision for accommodation at different points of existing routes.	Developing Camping Ground at Hatirgata and home stay facility at Bangal vita	1 – 3 years	Local entrepreneurs, NGOs, IUCN, Local Administration,
Income Generation Activities	No organized contribution to the income of local people from tourism or related activities.	Exploring the possibilities for suitable handicraft and souvenir making. Preparing the tribal people for cultural performance. Open air platform be established for that at Bangal vita	1 – 3 years	BSCIC, NGOs, handicraft training institutions, Local administration.
	Lack of business knowledge of the craftsmen	Training on business knowledge	2-3 years	IUCN, NGOs,

Involvement of Tour Operators	Tour operators are not aware of the tourism products in Tanguar haor	Preparing creative media for relaying information to tour operators (e.g. picturesque map).	In earlier stage of tourism development	IUCN, MoEF, MoCAT, Tour Operators.
	Selection and Orientation of Tour operators	Preparing training materials for orientation.	In earlier stage of tourism development	IUCN, MoEF, TOAB
Planning, Marketing, Promotion, & Research	Development of integrated Tourism	Formulating and implementing Tourism Master Plan for all wetlands including Tanguar haor	Master Plan for 5 years	MoEF, BTB, BPC, DU, IUCN, TOAB
	Need for tourism brand and marketing plan	Integrated tourism marketing plan to promote and develop tourism	Short and Long term	MoEF, BTB, BPC, DU, IUCN, TOAB
	Identifying the tourism products, both for short term and long term.	Turning the haor into tourism hub in planned way with a view to alleviate poverty through tourism.	Immediately and will continue.	MoEF, BTB, BPC, DU, IUCN, TOAB
Public Private & Community Partnership	Threat for ecological imbalance	Making people aware about sustainable ecotourism in a collaborative manner	Continuous	Tour operators/local community/ local administration/MoEF/ IUCN
	Availability of Investment Capital	Build up tourism infrastructure, services and facilities	Immediately and will continue.	Local entrepreneurs, Financial institutions, NGOs, Donor agencies, IUCN, Local Administration
	Ensuring safety and security to the tourists	Help Branding through creating positive experiences	Continuous	Local people, local Administration, Tourist police, MoEF.

Conclusion:

Tanguar haor, as yet, can be termed as the virgin tourism treasure of Bangladesh. In many countries of the world, the wetlands including big lakes, swamp forests etc. have been turned into tourist destinations very successfully. Keeping in mind the ecological and environmental issues, they have created big establishments including the flora and fauna museums in those

areas. We can develop some innovative infrastructural facilities in Tanguar haor for the tourists.

As an alternative destination Tanguar haor will become a popular destination in near future as the south-eastern part of Bangladesh, specially Cox's Bazar, has become less attractive to many of the tourists because of lack of diversified touristic activities excepting rinsing the legs in the waters of the Bay of Bengal. Beside presently the people are becoming much conscious about the pollutions created by them endangering the ecology and the environment. As an alternative recreation and knowledge gathering source, more and more people are increasingly preferring solitary destinations. Bird watching is becoming a popular tourism event in Bangladesh.

Besides, boating through huge waters of the picturesque haor during monsoon can be turned into a very attractive tourism exercise for the sunlust tourists. Therefore Tanguar haor has the prospect of offering tourism services in both the seasons. Expansion of tourism spans will create opportunities for the local community to be involved in additional economic activities. This will raise the level of their life style and standard of living.

For this purpose, motivating and involving the local people in tourism activities, creating area-wise community based tourism organizations, management of tourism organizations and activities, empowering the tourism organizations, identifying the tourism activities, developing short term and long term touristic zones etc. are inexorable.

Fortunately, IUCN,B has created the basic organizational facilities in different villages of Tanguar haor. They have also trained up the people there on different alternative economic activities. Total Tanguar haor area falls under Haor management committees. These people are committed to change their lots and consequently have dreams for a better tomorrow. Consequently, a fertile environment is existing there to involve the local people in tourism activities as an alternative source of income. However, as the local people are still very poor, government and donor agencies may come forward to finance for the tourism establishments like shallow boats, houseboats(boatels), walk ways, watch towers, etc. Local people should also be given training on hospitality management, catering, guiding, waste management and other tourism related activities.

The concept of Public Private Community Participation (PPCP) may be implemented there by inviting the private sector to invest in building tourism infrastructure; and motivating and involving the community in developing the plans at the grass root levels, managing the establishments, overseeing and monitoring the activities, and sharing the profit.

Lastly, Tanguar haor should be declared as an exclusive protected tourist zone where, no tourist should be allowed to enter and roam into haor area without the help and guidance of trained guides. It will reduce scope for pollution. The tour operators have to work in close liaison with the local guides and the CBT managements.

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